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PROTECTIVE EFFECT OF *AERVA LANATA LINN.*, FLOWER EXTRACT AGAINST IMMOBILISATION STRESS INDUCED GASTRIC ULCERS IN RATS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to assess the effect of ethanolic extract of *Aerva lanata linn.*, flower in experimentally immobilization stress induced Gastric ulcers in rats. Rats were divided into six different groups each having six. Group 1 served as a control, Group 2 received immobilisation stress (daily 1hr), Group 3, 4 and 5 served as extract treatment groups and received 50, 100, & 200 mg/kg orally, ethanolic extract of *Aerva lanata* flower and Group 6 served as standard group was received Ranitidine (20 mg/kg) orally. All the treatment protocols followed 15 days and after which rats were sacrificed, blood and stomach were taken for biochemical and Ulceration studies, respectively. The immobilisation stress treated group rats (G2) showed variable increase in serum Total protein, Total cholesterol, Triglyceride's, Glucose, ALT, and ALP levels. Administration of ethanolic extracts of *Aerva lanata linn.*, flower significantly prevented immobilisation stress induced elevation in the levels of serum diagnostic enzymes alanine amino transferase (ALT) and alkaline phosphatase (ALP), levels in experimental groups of rats. Moreover, total protein levels were significantly increased in treatment groups. The effect of extract was compared with a standard drug (Ranitidine). The changes in biochemical parameters were supported by histological profile. It is concluded that the ethanolic extract of *Aerva lanata* flower protects against immobilisation stress induced gastric ulcers in rats. In the present study treatment with *Aerva lanata flower* extract significantly decreased the elevated levels of Glucose, ALT, ALP, Triglycerides, glucose and increased the levels of Total proteins. From the results indicated that the ulcer protective activity of *Aerva lanata* flower may be due to the presence of several biochemical compounds. It is thus apparent that *Aerva lanata* possesses an ulcer protective activity.

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INTRODUCTION

Plants have always been a major component of traditional system of healing in developing countries, which have also been an integral part of their history and culture. Medicinal plants offer alternative remedies with tremendous opportunities. Many traditional healing herbs and plant parts have been shown to have medicinal value especially in the rural areas and that these can be used to prevent and cure several human diseases [1].

Even today, majority of the world population depends on herbal healthcare practice. The strategic importance of reviving indigenous medical practices to provide safe and affordable primary healthcare to the people of the world is now recognized [2]. During the last two decades or so, WHO's health Assembly has passed a number of resolutions in response to this resurgence of interest in the study and use of traditional medicines and in recognition of the importance of medicinal plants to health care of people in many developing countries (Subramoniam, 2001). India has rich medical heritage with a large number of traditional practices, systems and medicines as a part of its total health care scenario, some of them are more than 3,000 years old [3].

These systems utilize the resources of plant and animal kingdom. Plants are the major source among them, as they are a treasure house of potential drugs. The Indian systems of medicine use around 8,000 species of plants which include trees (33%), herbs (32%) shrubs (20%), climbers (12%) and epiphytes, grasses, lichens, ferns and algae put together (3%). Among 2,000 drugs being used in curing human ailments in India, only 200 are of animal origin, 300 of mineral origin and the rest 1500 drugs are extracted from various plants. Modernization is posing serious threats to medicinal plants and associated systems. Public are attracted to the modern system of medicine, which provides quick relief, at lower cost. But, in recent times, there has been an increasing awareness about the significance of medicinal plants and their use [4]. There has been revival of interest in knowing about many medicinal plants and their intermediates are inherently safer and more efficacious than the modern, potent synthetic drugs which very often produce undesirable side effects in man [5].

This prompted the people to return to the ancient and traditional system of phyto-medicines or herbal medicines. With the result, the use of natural medicines or herbal drugs has gained momentum and the demand for herbal raw drugs and other products is increasing many fold. However, the great block in promoting the use of herbal drugs are lack of the scientific evaluation and standardization [6]. Further, confusion in the identification of medicinal plants and their substitutes, adulteration, lacking valid and reliable scientific information for their therapeutic efficacy are some of the major problems concerned. Standardization of herbal medicines and quality control of the plant raw materials used as phyto – drugs are the most important challenges in bringing any of the acceptances of concerned people.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant materials

The plant material of *Aerva lanata* linn., was collected from the market of Ramakrishnapur, Adilabad and identified by the Department of Pharmacognosy of our institute. A voucher specimen has been kept in the department for further reference.

Chemicals

Total bilirubin, Total protein, Alanine Transaminase (ALT) and Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) were assayed by using kits. All the drugs, chemicals and reagents used for biochemical estimation were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, USA.

Animals

Male and female Wistar albino rats, weighing about 150 - 200 g were obtained from National Institute of Nutrition, Hyderabad and used in the experiments. The protocol was approved by the Institutional Animal Ethical Committee (Reg no: MRCP/CPCSEA/IAEC/2013-14/MPCOL/23). Animals were kept in the animal house at an ambient temperature of 25°C and 45-55% relative humidity, with 12 h each of dark and light cycles. Animals were fed pellet diet and water *ad-libitum*.

Preparation of the plant extract

The plant material of *Aerva lanata* flower is ground to coarse form and this dried powder was used for extraction. Extraction was done. Take ingredients in the round bottom flask; add sufficient water to the round bottom flask as solvent. Equal quantity of crude drug (500g each) in 1000 ml water is taken for extraction process. The whole apparatus kept aside for 3 to 4 days. In-between thoroughly the solvent was mixed for better extraction. After 4 days the contents were filtered, and marc was separated.

Further concentration of the extract was made by heating and evaporating the solvent kept in a water bath at 40°C, which finally gave a dark sticky residue. It was stored in an air tight container in a refrigerator.

Immobilization stress induced ulcers in rats

Albino rats were selected and are grouped into six groups of six animals each.

Group I: Control - These rats received 1 ml distilled water for 15days.

Group II: Positive control immobilization stress for 15days.

Group III: Immobilization stress + Alt extract (50 mg/kg p.o.) for 15days

Group IV: Immobilization stress+ Alt extract (100 mg/kg p.o.) for 15days

Group V: Immobilization stress + Alt extract (200 mg/kg p.o.) for 15days

Group VI: Standard-Ranitidine (20 mg/kg p.o.) for 15days

Experimental design

Stress-induced ulcer was made by immobilization. Animals in groups: 2nd group (Stress), 3rd, 4th, 5th group (stress+Alt) and 6th group (Ranitidine) were fasted for 12 hr, but allowed water ad-lib overnight. Immediately after 12hr fasting period rats of sixth group were orally administered a dose of ranitidine as previously described, rats of the 3rd, 4th, 5th group were orally administered *Aerva lanata* flower extract while rats. Prior rats were immobilized in supine position on a wooden board for 2 hrs. The four limbs of the rat were fixed at the 4 corners of the wooden board in a manner sufficient to prevent animal from turning or wedging itself, without hindrance of respiration. All the treatment protocols followed 15 days and after the rats were sacrificed by slaughtering.

Biochemical estimation

At the end of the study, animals were sacrificed by cervical dislocation with ether anesthesia, blood was obtained from carotid artery. The blood samples were allowed to clot for 45min at room temperature. Serum was separated by centrifugation using Remi cool centrifuge at 4000 rpm for 15 min and utilized for the estimation of various biochemical parameters like, ALT [7-8], ALP [9], Total proteins [10] and Total bilirubin [11]. The present study was to evaluate the anti-ulcer effect of *Aerva lanata* by using various biochemical parameters.

Histopathological studies

At the end of the experiment (day 15), all rats were anesthetized by ether and the stomach were excised out and put in normal saline solution. Stomach was cut into lower curvature to upper curvature. Then it will be easy to while observing the ulceration in stomach.

Statistical analysis

The results are expressed as mean \pm SEM. The evaluation of the data was done using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparisons tests. P values <0.01 were considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Table 1: Effect of different Treatment groups on ALT, ALP, Total proteins, Total cholesterol, Triglyceride's, Glucose in Immobilization stress induced Ulcer in rats.

Groups	ALT(IU/L)	ALP(IU/L)	Totalproteins (g/L)	TotalCholesterol(m g/l)	Triglyserides	Glucose(mg/dl)
Normal control	182.7 \pm 8.136	0.7432 \pm 0.0402	7.472 \pm 0.3456	149.7 \pm 0.3232	89.72 \pm 0.765	89.73 \pm 1.762
Immobilization stress	1702 \pm 49.96*	5.340 \pm 0.3828*	4.143 \pm 0.3654**	229.7 \pm 0.1326***	129.72 \pm 0.654*	135.4 \pm 1.7653*
Imb+Alt(50mg/kg)	1219 \pm 53.70*	4.830 \pm 0.4527*	4.564 \pm 0.1432**	194.7 \pm 0.24323**	120.7 \pm 0.562**	123.72 \pm 1.865*
Imb+Alt(100mg/kg)	741 \pm 39.74**	2.490 \pm 0.04458	5.921 \pm 0.342**	188.3 \pm 0.7643**	110.6 \pm 0.845**	119 \pm 1.074**
Imb+Alt(200mg/kg)	452.7 \pm 20.06*	1.019 \pm 0.03275	6.972 \pm 0.16543*	164.9 \pm 0.543**	97.54 \pm 0.896**	107.5 \pm 1.876**
Ranitidine(20mg/kg)	241.1 \pm 2.172*	1.314 \pm 0.1434*	6.4034 \pm 0.342**	159.2 \pm 1.249**	87.6 \pm 0.784**	94.0 \pm 1.876**

Table 2: Effect of different Treatment groups on MDA, GSH and Catalase in Immobilization stress induced Ulcer in rats.

Groups	Treatment	MDA (nmol/g)	GSH (μ mol/min/mg)	CATALASE (μ mol/min/mg)
I	Normal control	49.7 \pm 2.907	16.77 \pm 0.657	15.58 \pm 0.056
II	Immobilization stress	104.17 \pm 7.07***	7.1 \pm 0.86***	4.976 \pm 0.046***
III	Imb+Alt(50mg/kg)	89.07 \pm 1.32**	9.76 \pm 0.15**	6.86 \pm 0.0896**
IV	Imb+Alt(100mg/kg)	76.06 \pm 1.94**	11.9 \pm 0.564**	10.87 \pm 0.045**
V	Imb+Alt(200mg/kg)	59.74 \pm 2.41**	14.56 \pm 0.784**	14.8 \pm 0.0546**
VI	Ranitidine(20mg/kg)	39.94 \pm 2.43**	15.74.09 \pm 0.895**	15.86 \pm 0.089**

Table 3: Effect of Treatment group on Ulcer index in immobilization induced Ulcer in rats.

Groups	Ulcer index
Control	2.89±0.58
Immobilization stress	5.11±0.15***
Imb+Alt(50mg/kg)	2.99±0.76**
Imb+Alt(100mg/kg)	1.69±0.90**
Imb+Alt(200mg/kg)	1.87±0.45**
Ranitidine(20mg/kg)	1.43±0.95**

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM n=6, *** p<0.001; when compared to normal control group and **p<0.01 compared to Immobilization stress were measured by ANOVA followed by Dunnett's-test.

Figure 1: Effect of Treatment group on Ulcer index in immobilization induced Ulcer in rats.

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM n=6, *** p<0.001; when compared to normal control group and **p<0.01 compared to Immobilization were measured by ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test.

Histopathology

Figure 2: Ethanolic extract of *Aerva lanata* (AltE) flower on Immobilisation stress induced Ulceration in stomach.

DISCUSSION

The results in immobilization stress induced model showed significant reduction in basal gastric secretion and inhibition of ulcers by aqueous extract of *Aerva lanata* flower extract (AltE). This suggests that the antiulcer activity of AltE on gastric mucosa may be due to the reduction of gastric secretion through one or more possible mechanisms.

When exposed to prolonged stress, rats develop gastric ulceration, enhanced colon motility with depletion of its mucin content and signs of physiological and behavioral arousal. In this model, we tested whether antidepressants (fluoxetine and bupropion), anxiolytics (diazepam and buspirone) or the novel nonpeptide corticotropin-releasing hormone (CRH) type-1 receptor (CRH-R1) antagonist, antalarmin, modify these responses. Fluoxetine, bupropion, diazepam and antalarmin all suppressed stress-induced gastric ulceration in male Sprague-Dawley rats exposed to four hours of plain immobilization. Antalarmin produced the most pronounced anti-ulcer effect and additionally suppressed the stress-induced colonic hypermotility, mucin depletion, autonomic hyperarousal and struggling behavior.

It is therefore, difficult to elucidate the relationship between the mechanisms of inhibition of gastric acid by AltE. The antiulcer property of AltE in immobilization induced model is evident from its significant reduction in ulcer index. AltE treated animals significantly inhibited the formation of ulcers in immobilization stress induced ulcers in rats and also decreased concentration and increased P^H , it is suggested that AltE can suppress gastric damage induced by aggressive factors [12].

The current data clearly demonstrated that AltE inhibited the aggressive factor, gastric acid secretion. The anti-ulcerogenic effect of the AltE may be related to its antisecretory action since acid is a major factor in the development of peptic ulcer. The current data also clearly demonstrated that the 200 mg/kg is more effective than the 100 mg/kg and 50/kg dose of AltE [13]. The ulcerogenic effect of stress induced ulcer is rapid and constant thus providing a particularly reliable model for investigating the mechanism of gastric ulcerogenesis and possible means for its prevention. Our results confirmed the suitability of the method, so acute and almost invariably prominent gastric ulcers were developed in rats that received immobilization stress. The exact mechanism of pathogenesis in the immobilization stress induced duodenal ulcer model is not fully known but hypersecretion of gastric acid, deterioration of mucosal resistance and promotion of gastric emptying are among the possible mechanisms [14].

In present study, immobilization stress induced ulcer model blood parameters such as, SGOT, SGPT, ALP, Total proteins, Glucose, cholesterol and Triglycerides are estimated (Table 1) [15]. The significant increase in blood glucose level was observed because under stressful conditions adrenal cortex secretes cortisol in man and corticosterone in rats [16]. Hyper secretion of cortisol helps in maintenance of internal homeostasis through the process of gluconeogenesis and lipogenesis [17]. Pretreatment with the AltE as well as reference standard drug significantly reduced the elevated glucose levels indicating their suppressant effect on hyper activity of adrenal cortex and maintained the homeostatic mechanism. We assessed the protective effect by antioxidant enzymes CAT and GSH in the ulcerated stomach of ranitidine pretreated rats [18]. Ulcer induced animals by immobilization stress showed a significant decrease in gastric acid secretion, when compared to that of normal control rats (Table 2) [19]. The pathophysiology of stress-induced ulcers is complex. The ulcers are produced due to the release of histamine, leading to an increase in acid secretion, a reduction in mucus production [20].

CONCLUSION

Serum parameters mainly in case of ulcer induced groups, there were increased in levels of Glucose, SGPT, ALP, Triglycerides, total cholesterol total proteins levels decreased. In the present study treatment with *Aerva lanata* flower extract significantly decreased the elevated levels of Glucose, SGPT, ALP, Triglycerides, glucose and increased the levels of Total proteins. From the above results indicated that the ulcer protective activity of *Aerva lanata* flower may be due to the presence of several biochemical compounds. It is thus apparent that *Aerva lanata* possesses an ulcer protective activity.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AltE	-	<i>Aerva lanata</i> flower extract
ALT	-	Alanine amino transferase
ALP	-	Alkaline phosphatase
CRH	-	Corticotropin-releasing hormone
GSH	-	Glutathione
Imb	-	Immobilisation
MDA	-	Melanoldihide
WHO	-	World health organization

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